

Rumphius: his life and orchids

Nora De Angelli examines the life of a botanical great and uncovers a tale of discovery and disaster

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The island of Ambon (top). The portrait of Rumphius (left) in *Herbarium Amboinense*, made by his son Paul August.

ONE OF THE most epic, fascinating but also tragic lives in the history of botany, is that of Georg Eberhard Rumphius (1627–1702), known as the Merchant of Ambon or the Blind Sheer of Ambon. A remarkable man, in his life he played the roles of soldier, prisoner of war, mercenary, sailor, builder, merchant, physician, biologist, writer, illustrator and, above all, explorer.

Rumphius is best known for his monumental achievement, *Herbarium Amboinense*, the first major record of the eastern Indonesian flora, describing and illustrating over a thousand new plants, including many orchid species. This seven-volume work had its own long and turbulent story, its publication delayed by earthquake, tsunami, fire, loss at sea and political embargo. Yet this masterpiece today stands as a model of excellent science done by a self-taught amateur.

Early life

Georg Eberhard Rumpf (Latinized as Georgius Everhardus Rumphius) was born in 1627, in Wölfersheim, a small city not far from Frankfurt, central Germany. His father was a master builder and fortifications expert who worked for Wilhelm I (1570–1635) and taught his son mathematics, Latin and draftsmanship. His mother was the sister of Johann Eberhard Keller, governor of the north-western Kleve region, near the Dutch border which explains his impeccable command of that language. Young Rumphius received a good education, learning Latin, Greek and Hebrew (Beekman 1999). Later, his father sent him to Hanau, to attend the Gymnasium Illustre where Rumphius became most interested in ‘the secrets of nature’ (the sciences) and ‘the muses’ (the arts), developing his two-sided, scientific and romantic, nature.

At the age of 18, he decided to leave Hanau and enrolled as a soldier to serve the Republic of Venice. In fact he was sent aboard a warship headed for Brazil to fight in the Dutch-Portuguese War (Peeters 2020). Taken as a prisoner of war, for the next three years Rumphius served as a mercenary soldier in a Portuguese foreign legion. In 1649, he returned to Hanau, worked on construction projects and studied Pliny’s *Historia Naturalis*, a work that became an example for his future research.

The house in Ambon where Rumphius lived in a picture taken in around 1910.

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Sale set for adventure

Following the death of his mother in December 1651, Rumphius enlisted with the Dutch East Indies Company and boarded the East Indiaman *Muyden* as a gentleman soldier. He never returned to Holland.

He was 26 when he arrived in Batavia (now Jakarta) in July 1653. In 1654, he was sent to Ambon Island where he was to spend the rest of his life. Ambon, part of the Maluku Islands of Indonesia, was the centre of the spice trade: cloves, nutmeg, mace and pepper. These commodities were worth a fortune and Rumphius became a merchant, though admitting in a letter his real purpose was ‘the elucidation of Amboina’s plants’.

In 1663, Rumphius met Joan Maetsuycker (1606–1678), Governor-General in Batavia, who allowed him to import several European botany books. Rumphius rose to become second in command of the region, under Maetsuycker, a position that enabled him to also work on a catalogue of all the plant species he encountered. This monumental work later became known as the *Herbarium Amboinense* (*Het Amboinsche kruidboek*).

Rumphius lived well on his success and obtained a house and a piece of land, which he turned into a small botanical garden. He was well known in the area for his ‘irreproachable character’, friendliness and knowledge of languages (German, Dutch, >>

Latin, Greek, Arabic, Hebrew, Chinese, Indonesian Malay and Ambonese Indonesian dialects).

Around this time, a woman named Susanna is first mentioned in documents and it is clear she was married to Rumphius (Meeuse 1965). The limited evidence suggests that Susanna was not Dutch, but of Eurasian, Chinese or métis origin. The couple were exceptionally close, working together on their studies of natural history. She bore him a son, Paul August, and two or perhaps three daughters. Rumphius referred to Susanna as ‘his soul mate’.

In 1667, Rumphius’s employment with the Dutch East India Company came to an end but Governor Maetsuycker extended his contract and granted him time to continue his studies. Life must have been sweet, but happiness was short-lived.

Tragedy strikes

By April 1670, aged 43, Rumphius was gravely ill, suffering from photophobia and excruciating headaches. His symptoms are typical of glaucoma, and within three months he lost his eyesight completely. Nevertheless, his work continued on *Herbarium Amboinense*, helped by his wife and his son.

On 17 February 1674 disaster struck again when an earthquake hit the island and Susanna and Rumphius’s two daughters were killed by the falling wall of a shop in which they were standing. Rumphius, waiting outside, survived and a contemporary account reports: ‘very sad it was to perceive that man sitting beside these dead bodies and to hear his lament’. In memory of his wife is the beautiful, fragrant white orchid *Pecteilis susannae* named.

Rumphius met further catastrophe on 11 January 1687 when his books and manuscripts

were burned in a fire that nearly destroyed the entire city of Ambon. Only parts of the *Herbarium Amboinense* and about half of its plates were saved. Rumphius dictated the lost chapters from memory and the manuscript was almost entirely re-written, being eventually finished in 1690.

The manuscript arrived in Batavia where Governor General Johannes Camphuys ordered the material to be copied. In 1692, when the copy was finally finished, the original was sent to Holland on the *Waterlandt*. However, the ship was sunk by the French in the Bay of Biscay (Peeters 2020) and the entire manuscript was lost for the second time. New copies were ordered, and these arrived safely in Amsterdam in August 1697.

In 1701, Rumphius completed the last part, the *Auctuarium* or final gift, and sent it to Batavia where it was copied and shipped to the Netherlands in May 1702. A month later, on June 15, Rumphius died, he was 57 years old. After his death, his son, Paul August, was appointed ‘merchant of Amboina’ and inherited quite a fortune in land and houses and the equivalent of about £2 million.

The first orchid descriptions

By the end of the 16th century, only 40 terrestrial orchid species had been correctly identified by European botanists. A century later, the number of species had risen to 55, but the describing and classifying of the plants was still in its early stages, lacking much of the accuracy required of a true orchid manual. Consequently, before his departure, Rumphius probably only had access to the few books published about the European flora, since tropical plants, and especially orchids, were little known at the time.

Herbarium Amboinense

One of the most extensive botanical works of the 17th century, *Herbarium Amboinense* consists of 876 chapters, 1,661 pages and 695 plates, in which are described 1,200 plant species, 930 with definite species names and another 140 identified to genus level.

It was finally published as a bilingual Latin and Dutch edition of six volumes between 1741 and 1750. Orchids are mentioned in volumes five (1747) and six (1750). The companion volume, the *Auctuarium*, was published in 1755. Thus, Rumphius’s complete life’s work finally saw the light of day more than half a century after his death. An English translation made by EM Beekman (died 1999) was posthumously published in 2011. The two oldest handwritten manuscripts are now safely stored in the Leiden University Libraries.

LEON GALICZENSTEIN

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Pecteilis susannae (left) was named by Rumphius in memory of his beloved wife.

Phalaenopsis amboinensis (above) is just one of the orchids Rumphius studied.

Isolated from European botanists and universities, Rumphius had to draw his own conclusions about the new, unexplored species he encountered, especially in the case of orchids, which he was able 'to recognise almost without fail'.

Today, it is accepted that somewhere between 1653 and 1670 Rumphius became the first to illustrate and describe the seeds, anthesis, flower and fruit development, flower structure, floral senescence, resupination (see pp40–41), pollinia and epiphytic growth of tropical orchid species, long before botanists based in Europe. He was one of the first to recognize the nature of orchid pollinia and draw conclusions on the function of orchid pollen. He observed, drew and described *Grammatophyllum* fruits and seeds, mentioning that they were like dust, sand or flour. *Herbarium Amboinense* also mentions other orchid fruits and seeds. By showing the spiralling grooves on some ovaries, Rumphius illustrated resupination. A cut inflorescence of *Grammatophyllum* allowed him to study flower development from anthesis to post-pollination.

He relied on local informants to furnish him with specimens and brief him on their medicinal properties, making detailed notes on habitats and their uses. Each specimen was named according to a pre-Linnaean system of nomenclature, listing its name in Latin, Malay, Ambonese, Javanese, Hindi,

Portuguese and Chinese. Poetic or even romantic names in Dutch were also added. Despite identifying the orchids as a group, Rumphius did not include them in a single volume of the *Herbarium*. Similar to the rest of the plants described, he arranged the orchids according to their usefulness. Thus, the scented terrestrial orchid he named after his first wife, *Flos susannae* (*Pecteilis susannae*) is included in volume 5 which deals with useful plants, while all other orchids are in volume 6 covering 'wild herbs thus far untreated'.

The published work of Rumphius stands as a fitting testament to the life of an original thinker and one of the most interesting, romantic and tragic figures in the history of botany. ○

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